

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

November, 05-06 2022
Ethno Complex Vrđnickska kula, Vrđnik

Implementation of SRS/fSRT in brain metastases

Igor Djan

*Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia
djanigor@yahoo.com*

Introduction: Brain metastasis from systemic cancer is the most common neoplasm among intracranial brain tumors. One of the modalities for metastatic lesions treatment might be Linac based radiosurgery (SRS) and fractionation stereotactic radiotherapy (fSRT).

Methodology: Planning SRS and fSRT is based on computed tomography (CT) scan with a slice thickness of 1 mm. All patients were and must be immobilized in a thermoplastic mask. The gross tumor volume (GTV) for each lesion was delineated on MRI with a slice thickness of 1 mm, after MRI-CT image co-registration where applicable. The planning target volume (PTV) is defined as GTV plus 1–2 mm for all dimensions. Treatment was provided within 2 weeks after planning the CT scan.

Results: According to results of the review based on two institutional experiences from two different radiotherapy clinics in Serbia with Linear accelerators Varian Edge, encouraging results were shown in group of patients with brain metastases. Most of the patients had up to 3 metastatic lesions and were treated with single dose in range of the 18Gy-22 Gy dosed on PTV or 80% isodose related with tumor diameter. In addition, fSRT dose which was used is 24Gy/3 fraction or 30-35Gy /5 fraction for tumor lesion with diameter up to 4.5 cm. Ongoing follow up shows that the majority of cases have partial response and optimal PFS in comparison with literature data. Detail statistical analysis is planned after full three year follow up.

Conclusion: Linac based radiosurgery and fSRT are powerful tools for brain metastases which should be used in patients with appropriate indications. This advanced radiotherapy technique can be used with or without systemic therapy.

Keywords: Linac based radiosurgery, fractionation stereotactic radiotherapy, brain metastases

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2022**

Urednik
Olivera Ivanov

Izdavač
Institut za Onkologiju Vojvodine

Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-15-7

CIP – Каталогizacija u publikaciji
Biblioteke Mатице српске, Нови Сад

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (2022 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress,
November, 05-06 2022 Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula,
Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. - Novi Sad : Institut za
Onkologiju Vojvodine, 2022 (Novi Sad : NS digiprint).
– 56 str. : ilustr. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200.

ISBN 978-86-82113-15-7

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 78911241